

Work Motivation And Performance Of Treasurers Of SKPD Sorong Regency Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effect of leadership, training, and competency on work motivation and performance of treasurers within Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah (SKPD; Regional Work Unit) in Sorong Regency. This study used census technique or saturated sampling of which population was about 153 treasurers of SKPD in Sorong Regency. The research instrument was questionnaires that the results were generated for data analysis. The analysis results were described in figures, tables, statistical analysis, discussion, and research conclusion. Furthermore, the results indicated that leadership affected work motivation, but did not influence job performance. Then, training gave an impact on work motivation as well as job performance. While competency affected work motivation and performance. Last, work motivation influenced job performance

Keywords: Work Motivation, Work Performance

Background

Globalisation has to lead to high demand and challenges to maintain *clean government and good governance*. This study focuses on problems that are faced by the local government, especially the government in Sorong Regency, in completing the criteria of financial auditing. The submission of financial reports from *Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah (SKPD; Regional Work Unit)* of Sorong Regency is often delayed that obstruct submitting its financial reports into the Audit Board of the Republic of Indonesia, the representative of West Papua Province.

Kepala Daerah as the head of a local government is the person who held the power of regional financial management as well as who oversee the ownership of all resources within its region. Then, the power is carried out by the Head of *Satuan Kerja Pengelola Keuangan Daerah (SKPKD; the Regional Unit of Finance Management)* as well as the Head of *Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah (SKPD; Regional Work Unit)*. Within SKPD, *Kuasa Pengguna Anggaran (KPA; Proxy of Budget User)* is an officer that is designated and appointed by the management of a respective work unit to manage the existing budget. Then, KPA appoints a revenue treasurer to receive, collect, deposit, administer, and report all regional income as the implementation of APBD (*Anggaran Pendapatan dan Belanja Daerah; Local Government Budget*). KPA also appoints expenditure treasurer to receive, transfer, administer, and report all expenditures as the implementation of APBD within a regional work unit.

In particular, this study explored the performance of treasurers within Sorong Regency. This study assumed that it was necessary to examine the variety of factors affecting the regional treasurers' work performance. As the regulation, all governmental officers are expected to maintain their professionalism as their main duties and functions. Therefore, this study intended to investigate the effects of leadership, training, and competency on work motivation and performance that were demonstrated by treasurers within *Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah (SKPD; Regional Work Unit)* in Sorong Regency.

Theoretical Review

Leadership. Leadership is dynamic and performs the usage of power. According to Daft (2002:49), leadership is a reciprocal that occurs between people; it also includes activities of different people with the various administrative paper bundle as well as with problem-solving activities. While Tangkilisan (2005) argues that an organization will succeed or even fail mainly considered by the existing leadership. Indeed, the style of leadership is one of the most important elements in leadership effectiveness (Sadeghi and Pihie, 2012). According to Tangkilisan (2005), there are various leadership styles, such as: (a) Autocratic and Hierarchical leadership that is identified as a top-down and autocratic; (b) participatory leadership that provides participatory of subordinates for decision-making; and (c) value-based leadership that is based on a solid and integrated value relationship among its fellow members.

Training. Training is an integral part of personnel management (Cowling and James, 1996: 215). It provides a process by which an organization can improve its employees' knowledge and skills into higher levels. So the employees are able to achieve high productivity, quality results, and low cost. In turn, these are able to assist them to gain a competitive advantage as well as to perform their excellent service. Moreover, Hauenstein (1998) states that a training program for assessors is based on the idea that the accuracy of assessment and feedback is very important for the organization and employee development. Although the accuracy of assessment is not always the main objective of the assessor. In addition, there are several types of training, such as Frame-of-reference training (FOR), Rater Error Training (RET) and Rater Variability Training (RVT). These are particularly designed to improve the assessment process. While Behavioral Observation Training (BOT) is designed to improve the detection, perception and recall behavior.

Competency. Competency is defined by Boyatzis (1982) as one's existing capacity that leads him to meet what is required at work, so the organization is able to achieve its expected results. Besides, Sinnott et al. (2002) draw competency as a critical tool to examine office duties and planning changes. In the minimum level, he delineates competency as (a) recognizing abilities, attitudes and attributes required to meet current and future staff based on organizational priorities and strategic exchanges; and (b) focusing on employee development efforts to eliminate the gap between required capabilities. Moreover, Spencer, and Spencer (1993) define competency as the basic characteristic possessed by an individual who deals causally in completing essential criteria to occupy a position. They also divide five characteristics of competency, such as motives (consistent willingness and cause of action), innate factors (character and consistent response), self-concept (self-image), knowledge (information in a particular field) and skills (ability to perform the task).

Work Motivation. Motivation is an essential feature to consider one's behavior. According to Wexley and Yukl (1988: 143), motivation is the process of which behavior is given and directed with positive energy. In particular, there are two elements in the motivation, i.e., the emergence of direction to be achieved and the presence of energy to be driven to achieve the goals. Furthermore, motivation can be interpreted with the need, desire, drive, or impulse (Toha, 1993). Lessening motivation can result from cognition differences that are derived from the variance between individual's self-concern and external factors. Therefore, leadership plays a significant role in how to find and establish harmony among employees in the workplace.

Employee Performance. Performance carries out organizational tasks that have been accomplished by employees within a certain time. Robbins (2008: 146) argues that performance is the achievement of organizational goals that are established from the quantitative and qualitative output, creativity, flexibility, reliability, or other things perceived by an organization. The prominence of performance can be in short-term and long-term formats. It can also at the level of individuals, groups or organizations. In addition, the management of performance includes a process that is designed to associate with organizational goals and individual goals. So both objectives can match with the organization's expectations for its employees. Indeed, employee performance can be measured.

Hypothesis Development

Leadership styles of a leader or superior within an organization that can be allowed by subordinates or employees will have a positive impact on employees' motivation. The more acceptance of a leader's style or leadership style, the higher motivation of employee will be in the workplace. In the research of Devarrapalli and Hinkes (2016), leaders who have an autocratic style will always motivate their team. Such leaders are able to afford their team with positive energy and motivation. In brief, a good leader should be able to work within a variety of circumstances as well as to motivate his or her team members promptly. Moreover, Putra *et al.* (2009) mention that there are four factors that affect employee performance, such as leadership, organizational culture, internal communication and individual capabilities. Then, Gopal and Chowdhury (2014) convey that leadership has a significant effect on work motivation. However, the result of research by Rahardjo (2014) shows different result that leadership has no significant effect on work motivation. Hence, this study hypothesizes that:

H₁ : Leadership affects work motivation.

The management of employee performance is a process that is designed to associate with organizational goals to individual goals. It is expected that there is a convergent point as the agreement between

organizational goals to individual goals. In addition, performance can be an action or execution of a task that has been accomplished by an employee within a certain time; and the performance can be measured. Therefore, some variables are indicated having an impact on performance, such as leadership, training, competency, and motivation. To the extent, previous studies like Rahardjo (2014), Shafie *et al.* (2013), Setyaningdyah *et al.* (2013), Hamidifar (2010), Putra *et al.* (2009), Fahmi (2009), state that leadership has a significant effect on performance. On the other hand, another study by Tobing and Syaiful (2016) conclude that leadership has no effect on performance. Thus, this study hypothesizes that:

H₂ : Leadership affects employee performance.

Training is the basis for an organization to develop employees. The employee is the big asset for an organization, so an organization needs to pay attention to the employee by providing appropriate training. For this, Gullu (2016) states when employees are trained, their work performance and motivation can be increased. If the employees believe that training programs bring benefits to their skills, so they will encourage themselves for increasing their work motivation. Indeed, training and development programs are needed to improve employee performance and motivation. In turn, work motivation is important for the achievement of organizational goals. The more training that is followed by employees leads to their higher motivation. In contrast, Shahzadi *et al.* (2014) find the negative relation between training and motivation in the workplace. The employees who are not satisfied with in-company training tend to decrease their motivation at work. While this study hypothesizes that:

H₃ : Training affects work motivation.

Employee performance depends on various factors. Yet training is considered as the most important factor for employee performance. Training is important to improve employee skills (Khan *et al.*, 2014). Effective training programs aim to improve employee performance. The training will delineate the gaps between current performance and perceived performance standards (Elnaga and Imran, 2013). Moreover, training is a form of investment that requires more time, effort and money; but this investment provides long-term advantages for employees and organizations. Accordingly, some studies (Elnaga and Imran, 2013; Ameen and Hanif, 2013; Sultana *et al.*, 2012; Khan, 2014) indicate that training can improve performance. Similarly, this study hypothesizes that:

H₄ : Training affects employee performance.

Competency is indeed an abstract appearance. It does not signify tangible material and dependent activity on individual ability. Thus, competency includes knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics such as values, motivation, initiative, and self-control. The higher or, the larger competency that an employee has will lead to the higher motivation that the employee will demonstrate in order to achieve what is expected. In other words, an employee's higher degree of ability will increase his or her motivation to work in the office. Therefore, this study hypothesizes that:

H₅ : Competency affects work motivation.

Competency has a very obvious and different meaning. It can be defined as a capability as the performance standard of an employee who is expected to contribute to the organizational performance positively. Competency demonstrates an implementation that meets the organization needs as well as the individual concerns. Likewise, employee competency will bring an impact on his or her performance that, in turn, will contribute to achieving its performance.

In addition, competence that is owned employees can affect the performance that needs to be achieved in the workplace. This means that the higher degree of employee competence refers to the higher level of work performance. According to Setyaningdyah *et al.* (2013), there are three factors that affect employee performance, i.e., competence, organizational commitment, and leadership. Moreover, other researchers like Lotunani *et al.*, (2013), Ismail and Abidin (2010) conclude that competence affects employee performance. However, another research conducted by Septiyani and Sanny (2013) states that competence has no effect on employee performance. Yet, this study hypothesizes that:

H₆ : Competency affects employee performance.

Motivation is defined by Wexley and Yukl (1988: 143) as a process in which the behavior of each individual will be given energy and directed to achieve what is expected. There are elements in the motivation including the particular directions that need to be achieved as well as the presence of energy that drives an individual to achieve the goals. In relation to the perceived direction, the employee performance is connected with what daily goals are expected to be accomplished in the workplace.

Besides, the existence of high motivation among employees will assist themselves finding ways and efforts to fix their deficiencies in completing the office duties. Therefore, the employees' high motivation will have a positive impact on the performance to be achieved. The research results of Salleh et al. (2011), Anas (2010), Fahmi (2009), Gani (2008), and Ridjal (2006) have indicated motivation influences performance. In contrast, Dhermawan (2012) find that motivation gives no influence on employee performance. However, this study hypothesizes that:

H₇ : Work motivation affects employee performance.

RESEARCH METHOD

The population in this study were the treasurers within SKPD (the Regional Work Unit) in Sorong Regency. There were 153 employees. The technique for sampling in this study applied a whole sampling technique from a population. It was called a census technique. Then, this study used research instrument in the form of questionnaires. While the data was analyzed as the results of the questionnaires. This study used SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) analysis technique. Furthermore, the data analysis results were described in figures, tables, statistical analyzes, descriptions, and conclusions of research results. All were based the arranged conceptual framework and research design.

RESEARCH ANALYSIS RESULTS

Respondent Identity Descriptions

The treasurers within SKPD of Sorong Regency who participated in this study were mostly males. They are 91 males (59%) and 62 females (41%). The majority of respondents aged over 40 years, with a total of 61 people or by 40%. Then, 12 respondents (8%) were ones with age category between 26-30-year-old. Moreover, this study took samples for respondents with relevant working experience. In particular, there were 101 people or 66% of respondents working between 1-5 years. The least frequency was 2 respondents or by 1% of treasures working more than 10 years.

Analysis Results

In this study, a structural model was designed to ensure whether or not the model matched with the data. Moreover, it assured the presence or absence of influence between variables being studied. Hence, this study also applied the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) model estimation. At this stage, the first thing to do was to make sure that the model had been in accordance with the data or the model was fitted. If the model had been fitted, then the hypothesis testing could be done. Furthermore, the results of structural model estimation analysis are presented in the following figure:

Figure 1
Full Structural Model

Prior the next calculation was done, the assumption test was utilized to ensure whether the arranged structural model could be used or not.

Hypothesis Testing Results

The following are the results of SEM testing with SEM coefficient value atau standardized value on each variable.

Table 2 - SEM Coefficient Value on Effects Between Variables

Causality Relations		Direct effect	Indirect Effect
Leadership (X1)	→ Work Motivation (Z)	0.210	-
Leadership (X1)	→ Employee Performance (Y)	0.017	0.070 (0.210 x 0.335)
Training (X2)	→ Work Motivation (Z)	0.383	-
Training (X2)	→ Employee Performance (Y)	0.232	0.128 (0.383 x 0.335)
Comptency (X3)	→ Work Motivation (Z)	0.392	-
Competency (X3)	→ Employee Performance (Y)	0.353	0.131 (0.392 x 0.335)
Work Motivation (Z)	→ Employee Performance (Y)	0.335	-

The coefficient for indirect effect was calculated as follows:

The indirect effect of leadership on employee performance through work motivation could be calculated by multiplying the coefficient of leadership effect on work motivation (0.210) with a coefficient of the effect of work motivation on employee performance (0.335). Thus, the coefficient on indirect effect of leadership on employee performance equaled to 0.07 (0.210 x 0.335).

The indirect effect of training on employee performance through work motivation could be calculated by multiplying coefficient of the effect of training on work motivation (0.383) with a coefficient of the effect of work motivation on employee performance (0.335). Thus, the coefficient of the indirect effect of training on employee performance was 0.128 (0.383 x 0.335).

The indirect effect of competence on employee performance through work motivation could be calculated by multiplying coefficient of the effect of competency on work motivation (0.392) with a coefficient of the effect of work motivation on employee performance (0.335). Therefore, the coefficient on the indirect effect of competence on employee performance equaled to 0.131 (0.392 x 0.335).

Hypothesis Testing

The following is Regression Weight and Standardized Regression Weight on modified structural equation model:

Table 3. Causality Tes on Regression Weight

Causality Relations		Std. Estimate	SE	CR	P-value	Results
Leadership	→ Work Motivation	0,210	0,070	2,834	0,005	Sign
Leadership	→ Employee Performance	0,017	0,082	0,243	0,808	Not Sign
Training	→ Work Motivation	0,383	0,140	3,274	0,001	Sign
Training	→ Employee Performance	0,232	0,168	2,083	0,037	Sign
Competency	→ Work Motivation	0,392	0,136	3,495	0,000	Sign
Competency	→ Employee Performance	0,353	0,164	3,293	0,000	Sign
Work Motivatio	→ Employee Performance	0,335	0,136	3,107	0,002	Sign

The parameter for the existence or nonexistence of partial effect can be known based on CR value (Critical Ratio). The first parameter was to compare CR count > 1.96 or -CR count < -1.96; then, there was an exogenous variable that influenced endogenous variable or endogen variable that influenced endogen variable. Conversely, if CR arithmetic < 1.96; then, there was no effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables or endogenous variables on endogenous variables. Yet, it could also be drawn from the level of significant $\alpha = 0.05$. This meant that if the value of significance was 0.05, there were exogenous variables that influenced endogenous variables. Conversely, if the value of significance was > 0.05; then,

there was no effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables or endogenous variables on endogenous variables.

Discussions

Effect of Leadership on Work Motivation

The result of causality test showed that leadership had a positive and significant effect on work motivation with $p\text{-value} = 0,005 \leq 0,05$. The magnitude of leadership influencing work motivation was 0.210. This indicated that strong leadership could increase employee motivation. Besides, the descriptive results demonstrated that leadership and work motivation was at the good level. Furthermore, the motivation of the treasurer working within SKPD (the Regional Work Unit) in Sorong Regency could be improved through leadership. Specific efforts that needed to be developed through leadership related to punctuality and communication skills. These were rated as the lowest compared to other leading indicators. Consequently, the style of leadership within an organization or institution could give an impact an employee's self-motivation. In short, the greater leadership style being accepted by employees would advance their work motivation.

Effect of Leadership on Employee Performance

The degree of leadership affecting employee performance was calculated only 0.017. This indicated that strong leadership would not lead to significant improvement in employee performance. Thus, the results of hypothesis testing are inconsistent with the previous finding that the leadership of a leader can have an impact on the employees' behavior or attitudes on their daily duties. Moreover, if a superior's leadership style was acceptable, so his or her subordinates or employees tended to give a positive response to the institution. In turn, the subordinates would perform their official duties as what had been given; this could improve the performance of the employees or subordinates as well.

In this study, the insignificant effect of leadership on employee performance is due to the different characteristics of Papuan community and people in other areas. The sincere and compassionate characters along with strong and severe leadership characters of the Papuan leaders sometimes influence their communication skills with subordinates. Therefore, strong leadership without good communication skills will give a bad impact on the performance of employees. Endro *et al.* (2017) conclude that the Leader give the task or job that really challenge and provide opportunities for them also to engage a creative process, propose a decision in solving the problem, it will provide added value to their own, and thus the performance of an employee will be increased.

Effect of Training on Work Motivation

The result of causality test indicated that training had a positive and significant effect on the motivation of the treasurers working within SKPD in Sorong Regency. The calculation of the effect of training on work motivation was 0.383; this indicated that good training could advance employee motivation. Thus, the current training will encourage employees to work better. While encouragement was considered as motivation for employees to achieve their perceived goals. Furthermore, the broader training opportunities for employees contributed to their greater motivation to achieve the company goals.

Effect of Training on Employee Performance

The result of causality test showed that the training had a positive and significant effect on employee performance with $p\text{-value} = 0,037 \leq 0,05$. The quantity of the effect of training on employee performance was 0.232; this indicated that good training could improve employee performance. In regard to the needs of the training process for employees within an organization, the government has crucially developed policies to improve the quality of employment. This idea is in response to the growth of employment demand in the labor market. Furthermore, training will increasingly improve technical skills and managerial abilities of employees. The result of this study was consistent with research conducted by Sila (2013) arguing that training can give a significant impact on performance improvement.

Effect of Competency on Work Motivation

The result of causality test showed that competency had a positive and significant effect on work motivation with $p\text{-value} = 0,000 \leq 0,05$. The magnitude of the effect of competence on work motivation was 0.392; this indicated that high competency could increase employee motivation. In this study, competency included knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics, such as values, motivation, initiative, and self-control. Therefore, the more competence the employees were, the more motivation the employees had to achieve what was expected. Likewise, the result of this study was consistent with the research conducted by Putra *et*

Figure 2.

Variable Contribution to Employee Performance

Figure 2 explained that the most dominant variable in improving employee performance in SKPD Sorong Regency was competency with contribution influence of 22,4%, subsequently work motivation (22,2%), training (19,6%), and leadership (0, 3%). Thus, the total contribution of these four variables to employee performance was 64.5%; while the remaining 35.5% was influenced by other variables.

Conclusion

The variable that mostly had a direct effect on work motivation was competency since it had the greatest coefficient value. This was followed by training and leadership. Then, the variable that mostly had a direct effect on the employee performance was also competency because it had the greatest coefficient value; then it was followed with work motivation, training, and leadership. Moreover, the leadership influenced on work motivation; in turn, work motivation affected the employee performance. However, leadership did not directly affect the employee performance. Leadership affected only employee performance through the mediation of work motivation. In other words, motivation fully mediated the effect of leadership on employee performance.

In addition, training affected the work motivation; and work motivation affected the employee performance. Then, the training directly affected the employee performance through the mediation of work motivation. It could be said that the work motivation partially mediated the effect of training on employee performance. While competency had an effect on work motivation; and work motivation influenced employee performance. The competency also had a direct effect on employee performance. Thus the competency could directly affect the employee performance or through the mediation of work motivation. In other words, the work motivation partially mediated the influence of competence on employee performance. Last, the implication of this study added the development of behavioral theory in relation to leadership, training, competence, work motivation, and employee performance.

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